

The Generation of Artificial Sensations by Living Beings and the Prediction of Behavioral Responses. The Concept of “Consciousness”.

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Abstract

Introduction

The notion of "Soul" belongs to the religious and mystical realm. However, in neurobiology and psychology, the term "Consciousness" is used. These two concepts share similarities, as both describe the capacity for self-awareness, empathy, imagination, dreaming, and thought in living beings. The main difference is that the mechanisms of "consciousness" can eventually be scientifically explained and understood. This article proposes hypotheses that explain the mechanism of "consciousness" functioning in the human brain.

Discussion

This article examines the functions of hypothetical brain regions that may be involved in generating artificial sensations, visual and auditory sensations, and predicting or planning actions. Additionally, it presents hypotheses about the structure of these hypothetical regions and suggests which real brain areas might correspond to these hypothetical parts.

Results

A functional theory explaining the mechanisms behind generating artificial sensations and planning actions in living beings is presented. During the work, several hypotheses about the

structure and functioning of the brain were discussed, some of which were developed based on analogies with perceptron neural networks:

- The hypothesis of network integrity, including biological neural networks.
- The hypothesis of unidirectionality in neural networks.
- The hypothesis of varying receptor input distances from the motor cortex.
- The hypothesis of artificial sensations.
- The hypothesis of predictive reactions.

1. Theoretical background

The hypothesis of network integrity, including biological neural networks:

This hypothesis is based on the structure of modern neural networks and suggests that:

- Like information in neural networks stored as a unified matrix¹, all memory in a living being might reside in structures responsible for storing and processing information as a single neural network of neurons.
- Such structures include parts of the brain with NMDA receptors², primarily the cerebral cortex.
- For the neural network to function fully, no information "transfer" between structures is required. Short-term memory can transform into long-term memory within these structures³, similar to how neural networks learn through connection changes⁴.
- Neural networks can generate responses, including calculations and logical reasoning⁵.

Hypothesis of Neural Network Unidirectionality:

- Postulate: Since any neuron can transmit signals in only one direction, signals within the neural network also move in a specific, non-random direction.
- Postulate: Cyclic signal movements can lead to loops without exit, so later layers should not have direct outputs to earlier layers.
- Similar to computer neural networks, the first part of the network typically handles input of patterns and sensations, while the second part processes responses⁶.

This theory uses the occipital-frontal direction of cortical signals as primary, matching the thalamus's input and output structure⁷.

Hypothesis of Varying Distances of Receptor Inputs from the Motor Cortex:

If signals from neurons that don't carry life-critical information can be combined in multiple stages, signals warning the body of danger must be used for fast instinctive or reflexive responses. There's no need for prolonged deliberation when taking a breath or withdrawing a hand from a hot object. Signals crucial to life and health, like those from nociceptors or chemoreceptors for CO₂, should activate effectors regardless of other signals reaching the motor cortex. Therefore, the entry points for such receptors are likely located very close to the motor cortex.

Figure 1. General Diagram of Hypotheses: the hypothesis of network integrity, including biological neural networks; the hypothesis of unidirectionality in neural networks; and the hypothesis of varying receptor input distances from the motor cortex.

1.1. Hypothesis of Artificial Sensations.

Based on the hypothesis of neural network integrity, if real sensations in living beings activate specific groups of neurons, then artificial sensations (thoughts, visions, dreams, hallucinations) can indeed be reproduced by activating the same groups of neurons⁸ without the activation of receptors. Activation of such neurons in humans is possible through neurons (bundles) originating from other parts of the cerebral cortex.

1.1.1. Artificial Auditory Sensations.

Based on the hypothesis of network unidirectionality, the structure responsible for auditory sensations (auditory dreams, auditory hallucinations) must connect the frontal part of the cerebral cortex with the auditory cortex. The most suitable candidate is the Uncinate Fasciculus⁹. This bundle connects the frontal part of the brain with regions of the temporal (auditory) cortex¹⁰ and is involved in processes related to speech¹¹. Its activation should lead to the activation of the auditory cortex.

1.1.2. Artificial Visual Sensations.

The structure responsible for visual sensations (visual imagery, visual dreams, visual hallucinations) must connect the frontal part of the cerebral cortex with the visual occipital part of the brain.

The most likely candidate is the Inferior Fronto-Occipital Fasciculus⁸. Controlled activation of the neurons in this bundle should lead to visual sensations. Uncontrolled activation could cause visual dreams or visual hallucinations.

In addition to these, other associative bundles may also exist. For example, the inferior longitudinal fasciculus might induce artificial visual sensations in response to auditory stimuli¹².

1.2. Hypothesis of Predicted Reactions.

In common usage and in philosophy, ideas are the results of thought¹³. For example, if a non-rational being, relying on its real desires generated by the motivation system, such as

hunger, implements a course of action, then a rational being can plan a response. Predicting one's behavioral responses should also activate the same brain regions that are activated during instinctive actions. For instance, before saying a phrase, a person might "say it to themselves"¹⁴ to check for errors and correct it. Similarly, if we try to "shout" something "to ourselves," we can feel the same muscles tensing as they do during regular speech¹⁵. However, to prevent real actions from occurring when these areas are activated, the motor cortex's actions need to be blocked. Essentially, this involves two structures: one for activating the motor cortex and another for blocking efferent pathways from the cerebral cortex.

1.2.1. Structure for Activation of Deliberate Actions in the Cortex.

This structure should connect the frontal part of the brain with areas slightly more dorsal (posterior) to the motor cortex. According to the hypothesis of unidirectionality, when these areas are activated, signals reaching the motor cortex should produce deliberate actions if they proceed efferently through the thalamus, or activate the frontal cortex if the signals do not reach the thalamus.

The most likely structure is the arcuate fasciculus.

This bundle covers multiple zones, including Wernicke's area and the motor area¹⁶.

Controlled activation of the bundle's neurons should lead to action planning, as this will activate the motor cortex. It connects Broca's area and Wernicke's area¹⁷ and this bundle may be responsible for subvocalization.

1.2.2. Structure (Action Filter) for Blocking Actions (Efferent Pathways) from the Cortex.

To prevent real actions during action planning through the activation of neural bundles, it is necessary to disconnect the pathways from the motor cortex to the thalamus, as mentioned earlier. The structure responsible for blocking specific motor cortex signals must be large enough to selectively transmit some signals to the thalamus while blocking others, turning actions into covert desires. Functionally, this structure should resemble a three-dimensional array of "relays" that either pass or block certain signals depending on a control signal and should have GABA receptors throughout to block signals from any efferent pathways. The first dimension of the

structure should correspond to a specific effector, the second to the strength of the impact (muscle effort), and the third to control signals. The largest structure that fits this role is the putamen¹⁸. Control of the putamen may occur through frontopontine fibers of the anterior limb of the internal capsule, as suggested by the activation of the lower frontal cortex during subvocalization¹⁹. The globus pallidus is a smaller structure that is more suited to completely, rather than selectively, blocking signals, such as during sleep²⁰. The claustrum is too thin²¹, and the distance between the insular lobe and the putamen is insufficient to accommodate controlling axons.

Figure 2. General Diagram of Connections between the Cerebral Cortex, Thalamus, and Putamen. (The usual view of the brain is rotated 90 degrees)

Conclusions.

This article proposes hypotheses explaining the mechanism of the emergence of artificial sensations and predicted reactions in the brain. It has been suggested that the activation of specific neural bundles, such as the uncinate fasciculus and the inferior fronto-occipital fasciculus, may induce auditory and artificial visual sensations. At the same time, the arcuate fasciculus is possibly responsible for the activation of deliberate actions. In cases where a being plans an action without executing it, the putamen is proposed to be involved in blocking actual movements.

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